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FLASH

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AUTHOR(S): Melissa Balzarotti, Consorzio Italbiotec (ITB)
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Executive Summary

The Preliminary Exploitation Plan (PEP) for the FLASH project serves as a strategic framework designed to maximize the long-term impact and utilization of project outcomes. FLASH aims to revolutionize healthcare financing by addressing critical health challenges.

This document outlines the foundational strategies and methodologies for exploiting the innovative results of FLASH during the project's third and fourth years and beyond its conclusion. It proposes an efficient workflow for the implementation of the Exploitation Strategy which will serve as a guide also for the development of the Final Exploitation Plan.

The Preliminary Exploitation Plan aims to identify potential stakeholders (policymakers, healthcare companies, insurance companies, etc.), Potential Exploitable Results and outline possible exploitation roadmaps. Below are reported the results identified.

1. **Index of Resilience to Assess the Performance of Hospital Systems**
2. **Index of elasticity of health funding**
3. **Tool for forecasting the budget impact of new technologies**
4. **Decision Model for Adopting Pre-Market Technologies**
5. **Patient mobility reimbursement methodology**
6. **Policy recommendations on cross-border patient mobility**
7. **Evidence on the comparative effectiveness of information provision and financial incentives**
8. **Guidelines on payment systems and incentives**
9. **Identification of the financial circumstances contributing to integration of care**
10. **Report on digital health access**
11. **Research/policy report describing the best practices for the provision of digital health services by doctors**

The Exploitation Strategy of FLASH results entails the presentation and dissemination of its results through workshops and events targeted at key stakeholders like policymakers as well as the publication of results in high-impact academic journals. For some of FLASH results it will be possible to explore commercialization and integration in healthcare systems. Also, collaborations with organizations, regulatory bodies at regional and EU level and NGOs will be explored as a means to exploit some of the results of the project

In terms of exploitation, in its first two years, FLASH has achieved significant progress, including stakeholder engagements, dissemination events, and the publication of journal articles.

Moving forward, the plan will be refined to incorporate emerging insights, ensuring the successful delivery of the Final Exploitation Plan (D9.4).

This document represents a crucial step in leveraging FLASH results to transform European healthcare systems into more adaptive, efficient, and sustainable models.

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Glossary of terms

AZERO: AziendaZero

DRG: Diagnosis-Related Group

ES: Exploitation Strategy

EU: European Union

GA: Grant Agreement

HIF: Health Insurance Fund

ICS: Institut Català de la Salut

IPR: Intellectual Property Rights

ISPOR: International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Outcomes Research

MDC: Major Diagnostic Categories

PEP: Preliminary Exploitation Plan

PERS: Potential Exploitable Results

TEU: Treaty on European Union

WP: Work Package

1. Introduction

The **Preliminary Exploitation Plan** (PEP) will serve as a guide during the third and fourth year of FLASH and after the project conclusion for the exploitation of the results and innovations achieved within FLASH.

The FLASH project intends to be a game-changer in the European integrated healthcare system. By focusing on budget allocation and financing of health services within a specific budget with a multidisciplinary approach, the project conducts an extensive investigation of healthcare financing mechanisms across Europe. It tries to pinpoint and investigate the most significant factors that underline the link between the major problems facing healthcare systems and their funding. It also intends to provide evidence on the ability of existing financing mechanisms and contracts to address such challenges and study new solutions to achieve more effective, efficient and equitable healthcare systems.

FLASH has **four specific objectives**:

- Defining financing models that address health needs in an efficient and equitable way.
- Identifying the key determinants of resilience of healthcare systems in order to improve the ability to face extreme events, as well as long-term structural changes.
- Providing guidance on how better integration of healthcare services could enhance effectiveness and efficiency of healthcare provision.
- Contributing to a better understanding of existing incentives and to the development of new ones.

1.1. Objectives

The **Preliminary Exploitation Plan** of the FLASH project aims to establish the groundwork for maximizing the long-term impact and utilization of project results. It focuses on creating clear exploitation pathways, enabling stakeholders to effectively leverage innovative outcomes from the project. An element of importance of this plan is to safeguard intellectual property (IP) through appropriate strategies that ensure partners can fully exploit their results while avoiding conflicts and adhering to local and European IP regulations. The PEP outlines various exploitation routes, including direct use of project innovations by partners, licensing agreements with European firms, and ensuring sustainability beyond the project duration by fostering relationships with healthcare industries and policymakers. It is important to note that the characteristics of the FLASH research activity imply that policy makers are the main target of exploitation activities. However, the possibility of identifying specific areas where the private sector could be involved is also being carefully considered.

The key objectives of this deliverable are:

- Guarantee the proper utilization of the project results
- Facilitate the **commercial** and **social** exploitation of the project results
- Ensure the **protection** and exploitation of the project results by all partners

- Implement **synergies** with other projects or EU initiatives: collaborating with other EU initiatives to enhance the dissemination and exploitation of the project results.

These will be achieved through the implementation of the following aspects:

- **Identification of Potential Exploitable Results** (PERs), such as new methodologies, software, data, standards, publications, policy recommendations, or other intellectual property.
- **Assess exploitability**: evaluate the exploitability potential of each identified result (alternative solutions, competitors, target market and stakeholders).
- **Intellectual Property Rights** (IPR) potential: assess whether the result can be protected through patents, copyrights, trademarks, or trade secrets. Ensure the result aligns with broader EU policies and priorities to enhance its exploitation potential
- **Prioritize results** and focus on those with high impact and high feasibility for exploitation.
- **Develop exploitation strategy**: identify potential routes for each PER (commercialization, presentation to stakeholders, licensing, spin-offs, etc.). Consider forming strategic partnerships with industry, academia, or other entities to facilitate exploitation.

1.2. Structure of the Preliminary Exploitation Plan

This deliverable is meant to serve as a guide for the implementation of the **Exploitation Strategy** (ES) for the FLASH project. It highlights the workflow that permitted to draft this document and that will be implemented for the development of the deliverable **D9.4 – Exploitation Plan**. It provides an overview of the results already achieved and the ones that are under development. These are characterized in terms of type of result, alternatives, stakeholders and roadmap for their efficient exploitation. Since not all the results are tangible products or tools, it was not possible to identify the target market or the alternative solutions for all the exploitable results.

This document is meant to be a preliminary version of the Exploitation Plan of the project, so during the next two years it will be updated according to the partners' needs and the implementation of FLASH activities.

1.3. Workflow for the implementation of the Exploitation Strategy

The workflow for implementing the Exploitation Strategy (**Figure 1**) serves as a comprehensive roadmap, ensuring that the project's results are not only identified but also strategically exploited for future impact. This multi-stage process begins with the **identification of Exploitable Results**. In this stage, all the key project results are meant to be identified through discussion with project partners. The different types of results are new knowledge, methods and tools: activities and new partnerships & stakeholders' engagement; these are detailed in **Section 2.1**.

The next phase, the **stakeholder mapping**, involves a detailed identification of relevant stakeholders, namely policymakers, insurance companies, and healthcare sector entities. This step is crucial for aligning the project's objectives with the interests and needs of key industry players, ensuring that the exploitation strategy

addresses practical market requirements. The workflow then progresses to 1-1 **meetings with project partners**, where strategic discussions take place to understand each partner’s unique needs. These meetings are also an essential platform for assessing potential intellectual property (IP) concerns. Finally, the workflow culminates in the **implementation of the Exploitation Strategy**; an essential part of the strategy will be identifying appropriate tools and channels to ensure that the project results reach the relevant stakeholders such as policy makers: the strategy also includes an evaluation of the method and tools developed in FLASH and their possible commercial exploitation. Simultaneously, the strategy addresses IP valorization, focusing on the novelty, originality, market potential, know-how, applications, and services associated with the project’s outcomes. By progressing through each of these stages methodically, the project ensures that both the **PEP** and the **Final Exploitation Plan** are thorough, robust, and positioned for maximum impact. This phased approach not only strengthens the immediate deliverable but also establishes a solid foundation for long-term sustainability and value creation.

Figure 1. Workflow for the implementation of the Exploitation Strategy

2. Exploitation Strategy

2.1. Potential Exploitable Results

The PEP is meant to highlight the Potential Exploitable Results of FLASH; these results could change in the course of the next years of the project, and it will be responsibility of the Consortium to keep this document up to date, in preparation for the D9.4 – Exploitation Plan.

To ensure the successful exploitation and practical application of the project's results, their classification plays a pivotal role. By categorizing the results, we can create a structured approach to highlight their relevance and accessibility to different stakeholders. These results will contribute not only to academic progress but also to practical innovation, enabling ongoing collaboration and future FLASH – Flexible Approaches to Support Health through financing

advancements. The results are expected to foster meaningful partnerships, improve stakeholder engagement, and create long-lasting impacts across various sectors.

The possible categories for the classification of the results are:

- **New Knowledge:** deliverables or public reports which contain the findings of FLASH research.
- **Methods and tools:** the tangible outputs which will be developed, used, replicated, modified and scaled throughout the course of the project.
- **Activities:** online or residential events such as workshops, webinars, open days, focus groups and roundtables implemented during the course of the project.
- **New partnerships & stakeholders' engagement:** verbal or written agreements in which partners of FLASH will develop new networks or alliances with each other or external stakeholders to collaborate in future undertakings.

2.1.1. List of Potential Exploitable Results

Table 1 lists the Potential Exploitable Results of Flash identified for each WP

Table 1. List of FLASH potential results

No. of result	Name of the results	Work Package
1	Index of Resilience to Assess the Performance of Hospital Systems	Work Package 2
2	Index of elasticity of health funding	Work Package 3
3	Tool for forecasting the budget impact of new technologies	Work Package 4
4	Decision Model for Adopting Pre-Market Technologies	Work Package 4
5	Patient mobility reimbursement methodology	Work Package 5
6	Policy recommendations on cross-border patient mobility	Work Package 5
7	Evidence on the comparative effectiveness of information provision and financial incentives	Work Package 6
8	Guidelines on payment systems and incentives	Work Package 6
9	Identification of the financial circumstances contributing to integration of care	Work Package 7
10	Report on digital health access	Work Package 8
11	Research/policy report describing the best practices for the provision of digital health services by doctors	Work Package 8

2.2. Exploitation intentions and process

In **Table 2** the exploitation intentions to guarantee long-lasting impacts of FLASH results are described.

Table 2. Overview of the exploitation actions for FLASH results

No. of result	Name of the results	Exploitation actions
1	Index of Resilience to Assess the Performance of Hospital Systems	<p>Once validated, the resilience index will be applied to evaluate European hospital systems. This final phase will enable the creation of a dynamic map, which, thanks to the free availability of index codes, will be regularly updated based on available data, to identify areas of fragility and resilience across the hospital network.</p> <p>To ensure broad dissemination and impact among policymakers, the project will develop materials such as policy briefs and workshops. Furthermore, dissemination through traditional scientific channels will inform experts in the field. Finally, all codes, documents and data used will be made freely available through open platforms.</p>
2	Index of elasticity of health funding	<p>The index will allow to compare countries in terms of elasticity of funding with respect to health needs. The aim is to inform policymakers about these comparative results, thus giving them the opportunity to identify areas for improvement of the policies they implement. The report on “funding formulas” will complement this achievement. The aim is to reach as many policymakers as possible through documents such as policy-briefs and workshops. The dissemination activity through the usual scientific channels will also indirectly impact, by informing experts engaged in interactions with policymakers</p>
3	Tool for forecasting the budget impact of new technologies	<p>Making the tool easy to access and to use for payers, even in situations where the information available is scarce. Exploring the interest of private industries to adopt the tool. Attempts will be also made to present it to other national authorities, starting from AIFA, the Italian national pharmaceutical authority.</p>
4	Decision Model for Adopting Pre-Market Technologies	<p>The team is working with Catalan healthcare policymakers to integrate a decision matrix into their frameworks, aligning it with strategic goals. The plan involves engaging stakeholders through workshops, consultations, and pilot studies with regional health authorities to refine and implement the model. Dissemination efforts include academic publications, conference presentations, and exploring digital scaling through partnerships with software developers.</p>

5	Patient mobility reimbursement methodology	The methodology will be disseminated through policy workshops, training sessions for practitioners, healthcare economics conferences, and policy-focused journal publications to enhance adoption.
6	Policy recommendations on cross-border patient mobility	The findings have already influenced an amendment to Czechia's Law 48/1997 Coll, allowing health insurance funds (HIFs) to contract foreign providers, though implementation awaits precise price difference data. Dissemination plans include workshops for stakeholder engagement, academic publications, and conference presentations to share insights, foster feedback, and build consensus.
7	Evidence on the comparative effectiveness of information provision and financial incentives	Engaging policymakers to optimize information and incentive strategies for enhancing primary care quality, equality, and teamwork, while maximizing resource efficiency.
8	Guidelines on payment systems and incentives	Our aim is to engage physicians and policymakers in a discussion on the role of incentives created by payment schemes for managing chronically ill patients based on the results of our experiment.
9	Identification of the financial circumstances contributing to integration of care	The exploitation roadmap includes publishing findings in academic journals and presenting at conferences like EUHEA and IHEA in 2025. Results will be shared with healthcare policymakers through workshops and briefings and discussed with local partners, Catalan health authorities, and the Dutch insurer to refine and implement policy recommendations.
10	Report on digital health access	The policy report on digital health access will be shared with stakeholders, including the Public Health Department and Regional Health Ministry. Findings will also be disseminated through high-impact publications and conference presentations to maximize impact.
11	Research/policy report describing the best practices for the provision of digital health services by doctors	A policy report on factors influencing phone consultations in primary care will be shared with key stakeholders, supported by scientific articles, conference presentations, and digital dissemination via LinkedIn and project websites.

2.3. Exploitation of FLASH results

The exploitation strategy of the FLASH project is designed to maximize the impact of its innovative results, ensuring they address healthcare challenges in Europe. The project's outputs entail a diverse range of tools, methodologies, and policy recommendations tailored to improve healthcare financing, operational efficiency, and system resilience. The results are developed with a focus on scalability and adaptability, catering to various stakeholders such as policymakers, healthcare providers, regulatory bodies, insurance companies, and academic researchers.

The exploitation of FLASH results will proceed through a multi-path approach, leveraging targeted dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and capacity-building initiatives. Below are presented the key strategies:

1. **Policymaker engagement and legislative influence:** FLASH results, such as the “Policy recommendations on cross-border patient mobility” and the “Evidence on the comparative effectiveness of information provision and financial incentives” will directly inform EU and national healthcare policies. Stakeholder-specific workshops and meetings with policymakers will focus on integrating findings into actionable reforms. Legislative bodies will be provided with evidence-based insights to improve cross-border healthcare systems, address quality gaps, and optimize reimbursement models.
2. **Integration into healthcare systems:** practical tools, such as the “Index of Resilience”, “Patient Mobility Reimbursement Methodology”, and the “Decision Model for Adopting Pre-Market Technologies”, will be piloted and integrated into healthcare management frameworks. Hospitals, healthcare providers, and regional health authorities will be key collaborators in validating these solutions. Pilot programs and demonstration projects are planned to facilitate real-world application and refinement.
3. **Market adaptation and commercialization:** results such as the “Tool for forecasting the budget impact of new technologies” will be explored for commercialization through partnerships with industry stakeholders, including software developers and healthcare innovators. These tools will be promoted as scalable solutions for addressing financial and operational challenges in healthcare systems.
4. **Collaboration with European Health Agencies and NGOs:** partnerships with EU regulatory bodies, public health agencies, and non-governmental organizations will aim to align FLASH outputs with broader EU initiatives. Collaborations will focus on integrating results like the “Report on Digital Health Access” into efforts to reduce digital health disparities and enhance healthcare access across diverse regions.
5. **Dissemination through academic channels:** the FLASH consortium will prioritize the publication of results in high-impact academic journals and presentations at international conferences.

To ensure the sustainability of FLASH results beyond the project duration, the consortium will establish strategic partnerships, seek funding opportunities for follow-up projects, and integrate outcomes into broader EU healthcare frameworks. To this end, the interaction with other initiatives addressing related topics is considered crucial and some initiatives have already been undertaken. With the project PRUDENT (<https://www.prudentproject.eu/>) the empirical determination of health needs and unmet needs has been identified as an area of common interest, where synergies can potentially emerge. Moreover, clear connection points have been identified between the contents of WP4 of the FLASH project and most of the activities of the HI-PRIX project (<https://hiprixhorizon.eu/>). In particular, HI-PRIX focuses on the regulation of prices and procurement of new pharmaceuticals, the financial and organizational consequences of which are studied in the WP4 of FLASH. A joint session between the two projects was

organised at the conference of the Italian Health Economics Association in December 2024. Contacts have also been established with the project INVEST4HEALTH (<https://invest4health.eu/>). After the participation of the Coordinator in the mid-term workshop of the INVEST4HEALTH project, a first online meeting was held in December 2024 and further meetings will be planned in the future to further explore synergies between the two projects. Given the aims of the FLASH project, particular attention will be paid to make sure the project results reach the relevant policymakers. A tool that we are planning to use is the preparation of periodic policy-briefs summarising key results of the project with potential impacts on policymakers' decisions. Distribution channels will include the project web page and social media, and other channels will be also explored. Another opportunity that is being explored is the presentation of the project results at events where policymakers are actively involved. Contacts have been established with the European Health Forum Gastein to participate in their next calls. This has been identified as an excellent opportunity, although the participation costs could be a potential barrier.

2.4. Potential Stakeholders

In the following table (**Table 3**) are listed the potential stakeholders of FLASH results. They include policymakers, regulatory bodies, health insurance as well as pharmaceutical companies, the research community and healthcare organizations.

Table 3. FLASH potential stakeholders

Stakeholders	Interest in FLASH project
<p>Policymakers and regulatory bodies at the EU national, regional, and local levels</p>	<p>This group includes national governments, regional and local authorities, and supranational entities such as the European Commission, along with regulatory agencies responsible for oversight of healthcare systems. These stakeholders are key to the FLASH project's objectives of developing innovative and sustainable healthcare financing models. They can use the project's outputs to design and implement policies that promote equitable and efficient resource allocation. Additionally, they ensure that the proposed financial models meet regulatory standards, supporting transparency, compliance, and governance improvements in healthcare systems.</p>
<p>Health insurance companies</p>	<p>Health insurance companies, both public and private, could benefit from the work of the FLASH project because they are closely involved in the management of health care costs and a large part of the financial system in the European health care context. They could be interested in identifying more efficient contracts and optimal reimbursement models that balance risk and ensure economic sustainability. Therefore, the FLASH project can offer them the opportunity to test new contractual mechanisms in a real-world setting and provide useful empirical data to reduce inefficiencies and improve transparency of processes. In particular, the results of the project can lead to increased customer confidence and better management of economic resources by reforming contracts with hospitals and improving reimbursement mechanisms to ensure greater user satisfaction.</p>
<p>Hospitals and healthcare facilities</p>	<p>Hospitals and healthcare institutions, whether public or private, are one of the key stakeholders in the FLASH project. The project's proposal to develop flexible financing models is closely linked to the operational needs of these stakeholders, especially in situations of variable demand such as health crises. They play a key role in implementing the proposed financing models, ensuring economic stability and responding more effectively to demand shocks such as pandemics or other emergencies. FLASH could provide</p>

	hospitals and health facilities with solutions to improve the use of financial resources, with innovative solutions to improve operational efficiency, reduce payment times and optimise resource allocation, contributing to a more equitable and sustainable distribution. This will have a direct impact on the quality of services provided, benefiting both patients and healthcare professionals.
Academics and Researchers community	Universities and research centres are key partners in the FLASH project to analyse and study health systems. Researchers will be able to use the data and results generated by FLASH to advance research on health financing models and their impact, and to influence public policy. The project will provide them with a unique platform on which to base future studies, contributing to scientific literature and providing useful evidence for policy makers and other stakeholders at the European level. Part of the FLASH activity also includes the production of original datasets, which will be available for use by other researchers willing to advance knowledge on related topics.
Pharmaceutical, biotechnology, health and digital industries	These industries are keenly interested in financing models that facilitate access to innovative treatments, technologies, and digital health solutions. The FLASH project offers insights into flexible healthcare contracts and reimbursement mechanisms, enabling these industries to adapt their offerings to public healthcare system needs while ensuring economic sustainability. Additionally, the project supports the development and adoption of new pricing models that balance access to treatments and financial feasibility. These industries also stand to benefit from the project's advanced forecasting tools, which can aid in planning for revenue streams and aligning innovations with healthcare system priorities. By fostering collaboration and providing actionable insights, FLASH aims to create a conducive environment for integrating novel treatments, devices, and digital solutions into European healthcare systems. The results of the project can also be used to negotiate pricing models that encourage the uptake of new technologies. Moreover, the industry can also benefit from the availability of more accurate forecasting models as those produced as part of the activity of WP4.
Trade unions and professional healthcare organizations	For trade unions and health workers' organizations, FLASH is an opportunity to ensure that resources are allocated fairly and that the working conditions of health workers are adequately supported. The results of the project, such as the proposal of sustainable financial models, can be used to promote policies that improve job stability and promote the well-being of health workers.

3. Exploitable Result No. 1: Index of Resilience to Assess the Performance of Hospital Systems

3.1. Characterization

This result involves the development of an **Index of Resilience** to evaluate the robustness and adaptability of healthcare systems during crises. Drawing from extensive research and stakeholder engagement, this index is designed to provide actionable insights for policymakers and healthcare administrators to bolster system resilience. The methodology emphasizes quantitative and qualitative measures that can be adapted across different healthcare systems.

Table 4. General information of Exploitable Result No. 1

Name of the Exploitable Results	Index of Resilience to Assess the Performance of Hospital Systems
Type of results	[X] New Knowledge

	<input type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Brief description of the result	The index assesses hospital system resilience to peak demands, helping policymakers identify critical areas and plan interventions. A tested methodology will map fragility across systems, with updates supported by open-access codes and data. The main outcomes of this task will include two policy report detailing the index methodology and the application to the European hospital system respectively.
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Partner/s responsible for the results	UNICT
Work Package related to the results	WP2

3.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

3.1.2. Target Market

N/A

3.1.3. Stakeholder

- Scientific community
- Policymakers

3.2. Exploitation Roadmap

The exploitation path for this result will focus on integrating the index of resilience into existing healthcare policy and management frameworks. Activities will include organizing workshops and develop materials such as policy briefs with policymakers, healthcare administrators, and academic researchers to showcase the applicability and benefits of the index. Targeted outreach to European health ministries and public health agencies will aim to establish pilot programs. Additionally, publishing in high-impact journals and presenting at international conferences will ensure widespread dissemination and adoption. Collaboration with private sector entities and NGOs will explore broader applications in crisis management and global health resilience strategies.

4. Exploitable Result No. 2: Index of elasticity of health funding

4.1. Characterization

The index aims to provide a novel quantitative estimate of the elasticity of healthcare funding with respect to health needs, with a focus on the distribution of resources from the central to the local level. The analysis will consider several proxies of health funding and several proxies of health needs. For the latter, both macro-data at the regional level and individual data collected through existing FLASH – Flexible Approaches to Support Health through financing

surveys will be used. Underlying the construction of such an index is the idea that more funding should be allocated to local entities with greater needs. The application of a standard methodology across countries will allow for a comparative analysis of the index.

Importantly, the inputs used for this analysis will be combined into an original dataset that will be made publicly available (Deliverable 3.2). Hopefully, this will stimulate further analysis to improve the understanding of the topic.

Table 5. General information of Exploitable Result No. 2

Name of the Exploitable Results	Index of elasticity of health funding
Type of results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders' engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	The index quantifies healthcare funding elasticity relative to needs, enabling cross-country comparisons and promoting equitable resource distribution
Partner/s responsible for the results	UNIVR
Work Package related to the results	WP3

4.1.1. Alternative solutions

While the topic of local redistribution of healthcare resources has sometimes been studied within countries, we are not aware of any comparative quantitative investigation. Moreover, the interpretation of the quantitative results of Deliverable 3.3 will be complemented by the qualitative analysis of Deliverable 3.1. The aim is to build on the analysis of alternative funding formulas adopted by different countries to identify features which are potentially associated with better or worse ability to address health needs with adequate funding.

4.1.2. Target Market

N/A

4.1.3. Stakeholder

Relevant stakeholders include all the actors (typically policymakers) involved in the process of allocation of resources from a higher to a lower level of the health system. Note that, although the quantitative analysis on which the estimate of the elasticity index is based focuses on redistribution from the local to the regional level, the drivers of better or worse ability to accommodate health needs can be expected to be the same for redistribution across different levels. For example, redistribution from the regional level to local health authorities is relevant in some systems. This widens the number of policymakers who can potentially benefit from the results of

the analysis substantially. Of particular interest in this respect is the interaction between UNVR, leading Task 3.1, and AZERO, which is actively involved in the process of allocation of financial resources from the regional to the local level in the Veneto Region.

Finally, the publication of the relevant dataset will provide researchers with the opportunity to carry out further investigations on the topic.

4.2. Exploitation Roadmap

The strategies outlined in **Section 2.3** will be pursued to maximize the impact of this result. The direct involvement of AZERO in the process of resource allocation at the local level is an important asset to make sure that results are accessible to policymakers and to reach them.

Publication outlets will be selected taking also into account their relevance for policymakers.

5. Exploitable Result No. 3: Tool for forecasting the budget impact of new technologies

5.1. Characterization

The aim of the development of the tool is to enable relevant stakeholders, and especially payers, to improve their ability to forecast the budget impact of new technologies when they reach the market. The tool can also be of interest for manufacturers aiming to forecast revenues of specific innovations over time.

The focus is mainly on new medicinal products, which, in recent years, have driven the growth of pharmaceutical expenditure. The tool aims to allow for the systematic application of Markov modelling to budget impact analysis. Compared to methods commonly applied in practice, this approach allows users to account for several factors that may have a significant impact on the budget impact over time, such as the impact of extended survival on the number of users, specific forms of *managed entry agreements*, prices changing over time.

By exploiting the fact that the structure of the forecasting problem has several features that are the same regardless of the specific technology, we design a tool that is flexible in that it can be applied to the budget impact analysis (BIA) of multiple technologies by changing the appropriate input parameters. Furthermore, taking into account the needs of payers who have to perform several BIAs with limited time, resources and information availability, the tool is designed to use only information that is easily accessible to payers at the time the new product is launched.

Table 6. General information of Exploitable Result No. 3

Name of the Exploitable Results	Tool for forecasting the budget impact of new technologies
Type of results	<input type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders' engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved

Brief description of the result	The tool aims to help stakeholders, particularly payers, forecast the budget impact of new technologies, especially medicinal products, using a flexible Markov modeling approach. It addresses key factors like extended survival, managed entry agreements, and price changes over time. Designed for accessibility and efficiency, it supports multiple budget impact analyses with minimal input requirements, catering to payers' limited resources and information availability.
Partner/s responsible for the results	UNIVR
Work Package related to the results	WP4

5.1.1. Alternative solutions

Payers are frequently faced with the need to assess the budget impact of new technologies eligible for reimbursement. Given the objectives of making these new, often costly, technologies accessible to patients as soon as possible, these assessments must be performed with tight deadlines. Moreover, the information available at that stage is often scarcer than one would wish. Given these constraints, payers often use very basic tools, based on spreadsheets aimed at combining information on prices with information on the number of patients eligible for the use of the new technology. These tools do not allow to address all the complications of the situation and provide a rather rough estimate of the budget impact over time, although this information is crucial for payer's financial planning.

A more accurate tool to use should be based on Markov models. However, these models, which are widely used in the practice of cost-effectiveness and cost-utility analysis, are seldom used in this context, even though the ISPOR guidelines for budget impact analysis acknowledge the desirability of their properties. The few existing examples of applications are academic, and they were developed on a case-by-case basis. This approach is not appealing to payers, as it requires significant investment in the development of a model that can be used only for one technology. A key feature of the proposed tool is that it is flexible, i.e. the same tool can be used for several technologies, by changing the input parameters, but not the model structure.

5.1.2. Target Market

Payers are our main target, given the significant number of budget impact analyses they are involved in, with tight deadlines and limited information. Our objective is to make the tool as accessible as possible by reducing the number of inputs needed to the minimum and by using a software that is as accessible and easy to use as possible.

Of course, payers' expenditure corresponds to manufacturers' revenues. Of course, knowing the profile of revenues over time is also crucial to manufacturers. In their case, the time constraint may be less binding than for payers and the information available may be slightly richer. However, based on our knowledge of the way in which the budget impact analysis is conducted by manufacturers, it is likely that that the software adopted does not allow to track the budget impact over time as

precisely as our tool will allow to do. In particular, the tool considers one additional dimension of analysis, i.e. the time since the beginning of a treatment, which is very complicated to incorporate into analysis based on spreadsheets.

5.1.3. Stakeholder

- Healthcare payers
- National and regional pharmaceutical authorities
- Pharmaceutical industry.

5.2. Exploitation Roadmap

In an attempt to reach both payers and manufacturers, the tool was presented at the 2024 ISPOR Europe conference held in Barcelona, the leading conference in the field.

Thanks to contacts established by BIOCAT, WP4’s leader, CatSalut (the Catalan Health Service) showed interest in knowing more about the tool. To this end, a meeting will be planned to illustrate it. Attempts will be also made to present it to other national authorities, starting from AIFA, the Italian national pharmaceutical authority.

6. Exploitable Result No. 4: Decision Model for Adopting Pre-Market Technologies

6.1. Characterization

The main result is the successful development and validation of a novel methodology for forecasting the financial and systemic impact of adopting pre-market technologies. This methodology is based on horizon scanning foresight analysis (PESTLE) and was tested through consultations with a diverse group of 25 experts via focus groups, interviews, and a questionnaire. The process reported in D4.2 not only validates the methodology but also serves as the foundation for the third deliverable, which will create specific guidelines for policymakers.

Table 7. General information of Exploitable Result No. 4

Name of the Exploitable Results	Decision Model for Adopting Pre-Market Technologies
Type of results	<input type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input type="checkbox"/> Under development <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	The result is a validated methodology for forecasting the impact of pre-market technologies, using PESTLE analysis and expert consultations. It forms the basis for guidelines in Deliverable 4.3.
Partner/s responsible for the results	BIOCAT
Work Package related to the results	WP4

6.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

6.1.2. Target Market

N/A

6.1.3. Stakeholder

- Policymakers
- Regulatory bodies
- Healthcare companies

6.2. Exploitation Roadmap

The team is actively collaborating with policy-makers within the Catalan healthcare system to examine in detail how this decision matrix could be effectively integrated into their existing decision-making frameworks, ensuring that it aligns with their strategic objectives and operational needs.

The exploitation of this decision model involves engaging policymakers, healthcare regulators, and industry stakeholders. Workshops and consultations will be organized to showcase the model’s capabilities and gather feedback for further refinement. Pilot studies will be conducted in collaboration with regional health authorities to integrate the model into their decision-making processes. Academic dissemination will include journal articles and conference presentations, while partnerships with software developers will explore opportunities for digitizing and scaling the model.

7. Exploitable Result No. 5: Patient mobility reimbursement methodology

7.1. Characterization

This result is a report presenting the methodology of price difference calculation of hospitalizations that are differently defined in different DRG systems.

Preparatory work has been conducted since the beginning of the project to ensure accurate and robust calculations of price differences. Specifically, the research team has started their work with MDC 14 – Pregnancy, Childbirth, and Puerperium. Further improvements, validations, and extensions of MDC 14 are necessary and will continue in the coming months. In the next phase, the team plans to identify homogenous groups within other MDCs (beyond DRG) to categorize both CZ and DE DRG groups, allowing for the precise calculation of price differences for non-homogenous hospitalizations using an econometric model. Simultaneously, a data request is being specified to both CZ and DE authorities to empirically verify the methodology for calculating price differences in non-identically categorized hospitalizations.

Table 8. General information of Exploitable Result No. 5

Name of the Exploitable Results	Patient mobility reimbursement methodology
Type of results	<input type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement

Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	Report presenting the methodology of price difference calculation of hospitalizations that are differently defined in different DRG systems.
Partner/s responsible for the results	CU
Work Package related to the results	WP5

7.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

7.1.2. Target Market

N/A

7.1.3. Stakeholder

- Policymakers
- Health insurance funds

7.2. Exploitation Roadmap

The team participated in a conference on cross-border healthcare issues between Czechia and Germany, held in Karlovy Vary on November 13, 2023, attended primarily by policymakers and health insurance funds. During the event, the project as a whole and the objectives of this deliverable were presented. Additionally, the project, with a focus on work conducted in WP5 and WP2, was introduced to the general public on November 9, 2023, during the "Week of the Academy of Science of the Czech Republic."

The methodology will be introduced through policy workshops targeting cross-border healthcare stakeholders, including national health agencies and insurance providers. Training sessions will be offered to familiarize practitioners with its application. Presentations at healthcare economics conferences and publications in policy-focused journals will aim to increase its adoption.

8. Exploitable Result No. 6: Policy recommendations on cross-border patient mobility

8.1. Characterization

This recommendations brings together inputs from different tasks of WP5. They classify patient mobility across Europe from economic and legal perspectives, introducing systemic gaps, and challenges in cross-border healthcare. At the the same time, recommendations are suggested. It serves as a key resource for policymakers, researchers, and healthcare administrators to analyze trends and design strategies to reduce disparities and inefficiencies resulting from the lack of cross-border patient flows in countries with different price levels.

Table 9. General information of Exploitable Result No. 6

Name of the Exploitable Results	Policy recommendations on cross-border patient mobility
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Type of results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	The recommendations analyze patient mobility in Europe from economic and legal perspectives, identifying systemic gaps and challenges. They provide strategies for reducing disparities and inefficiencies in cross-border healthcare, serving as a resource for policymakers, researchers, and administrators.
Partner/s responsible for the results	KZP, UNIVR, MCI, CU
Work Package related to the results	WP5

8.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

8.1.2. Target Market

N/A

8.1.3. Stakeholder

- Policymakers
- Scientific Community
- Regulatory bodies

8.2. Exploitation Roadmap

The findings will be disseminated through targeted engagements with national health authorities, and cross-border healthcare stakeholders. First success of the initiatives has already resulted in the amendment of the Law 48/1997 Coll on Public health insurance in Czechia which allows Czech health insurance (HIFs) funds to contract a foreign provider. The willingness of HIFs to do is missing though, as a precise price difference is yet unknown. This result is thus necessary to be perceived together with the exploitable result No. 7. Specifically, Czech HIFs are expected to contract German providers in those DRGs where the price difference is not extensive.

Workshops could be organized to share insights, gather feedback. Academic dissemination will include journal publications and conference presentations to enhance visibility and foster consensus among researchers and policymakers.

9. Exploitable Result No. 7: Evidence on the comparative effectiveness of information provision and financial incentives

9.1. Characterization

We analyzed the impact of two strategies to improve the quality of public primary care in Catalonia between 2010 and 2019: the provision of real-time information to healthcare professionals (via an online platform) and financial incentives to achieve specific quality-of-care goals. We evaluated data from 272 ICS primary care centers, covering more than 5.6 million patients, and examined the effects of these interventions on 63 quality-of-care indicators.

Our results demonstrate that providing information to healthcare professionals can be as effective as offering financial incentives. Indicators that were solely informed improved in 75% of cases, while those that were both informed and incentivized showed improvements in 64%. In addition to improving results, the interventions reduced variability between primary care practices, promoting more homogeneous and equitable care across the region.

Furthermore, adding financial incentives to already informed indicators did not lead to additional improvements. These findings suggest that offering updated information to healthcare professionals to monitor their clinical activity is a powerful and cost-effective tool for improving healthcare quality. In the long term, this strategy could be more sustainable and scalable in public health systems.

Table 10. General information of Exploitable Result No. 7

Name of the Exploitable Results	Evidence on the comparative effectiveness of information provision and financial incentives
Type of results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input type="checkbox"/> Under development <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	Rationale on the effectiveness of information and financial incentives to primary care professionals, for the design of more efficient quality improvement schemes.
Partner/s responsible for the results	IDIAPJGol
Work Package related to the results	WP6

9.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

9.1.2. Target Market

N/A

9.1.3. Stakeholder

National and regional authorities responsible for the organization and management of health systems.

9.2. Exploitation Roadmap

We have presented these results in national and international congresses on primary care and health economics (SEMFyC and EuHEA). Additionally, results have been published in *The Lancet Regional Health - Europe* (DOI: 10.1016/j.lanpe.2024.101102). This article will be shared via social media platforms and press notes from the institutions involved.

The results will be shared with healthcare policymakers through workshops and briefings. Academic dissemination includes journal publications and conference presentations. The findings will be further discussed with Catalan health authorities to explore broader implementation and refinement of the strategies. Collaboration with other EU regions will aim to replicate the model in diverse healthcare settings.

10. Exploitable Result No. 8: Guidelines on payment systems and incentives

10.1. Characterization

Our model assesses the dynamic incentives created by payment schemes for managing chronically ill patients. We evaluate capitations, fee-for-service, and pay-for-performance components. Particular focus is placed on how general practitioners' decisions influence the progression of a disease over time and the treatment options available in secondary care. We also consider how limited hospital capacity affects preventive effort by physicians. The laboratory experiment will test the predictions generated by the model regarding the effects of the different payment systems with medical students taking the role of physicians. From these results, policy implications for the implementation of the different payment schemes will be derived.

Table 11. General information of Exploitable Result No. 8

Name of the Exploitable Results	Guidelines on payment systems and incentives
Type of results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	Theoretical and laboratory experimental insights into the design of payment systems for the treatment and prevention of chronic diseases
Partner/s responsible for the results	UHAM, UNICT

Work Package related to the results	WP6
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10.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

10.1.2. Target Market

N/A

10.1.3. Stakeholder

- Scientific Community
- Policymakers
- Physicians

10.2. Exploitation Roadmap

A theoretical model has been built. Furthermore, a laboratory experiment has been coded and the recruitment of participants is underway.

The model will be validated through laboratory experiments, with findings disseminated via high-impact journals and international conferences. We aim to publish our results in a highly ranked international scientific journal. Furthermore, we will present our results at international conferences such as the EuHEA. Moreover, conference workshops with policymakers and healthcare administrators will focus on translating insights into actionable payment reforms. Collaborations with academic and industry partners will explore integrating the model into broader healthcare financing frameworks.

11. Exploitable Result No. 9: Identification of the financial circumstances contributing to integration of care

11.1. Characterization

We will consider integrated care in two settings: the Netherlands and Catalonia. We will perform policy evaluations of efforts to promote integrated care in both settings, working together in both cases with a local insurer. Our close collaboration with a local partner will ensure that our findings have a direct impact on local policies. Moreover, the team members are in regular contact with local policy makers and stakeholders. For instance, the team at the EUR organized a seminar on long term care in 2024 that was attended by individuals from the Dutch ministry of health, the ministry of finance, the Dutch Health Care Institute, and practitioners in the field of long-term care.

We will write a report containing the main overarching findings and policy messages (D7.3) that we will actively share with policy makers across the EU. Potentially, we will organize a policy seminar around this topic as well.

Table 12. General information of Exploitable Result No. 9

Name of the Exploitable Results	Identification of the financial circumstances contributing to integration of care
Type of results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools

	<input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	Evaluation of financial incentives/interventions to promote integrated care for older people.
Partner/s responsible for the results	EUR/IDIAP
Work Package related to the results	WP7

11.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

11.1.2. Target Market

N/A

11.1.3. Stakeholder

- Insurance companies
- Policymakers.

11.2. Exploitation Roadmap

The deadline for the report on integrated care is month 48. We have secured data access in both setting and are currently setting up the analysis. Academic dissemination includes journal publications and conference presentations. We intend to have the first results ready during 2025 and presenting these at scientific conferences like EUHEA and IHEA. The results will be shared with healthcare policymakers through workshops and briefings. The findings will be further discussed with the local partners, the Catalan health authorities and the Dutch insurer, to explore broader implementation and refinement of the policy suggestions.

12. Exploitable Result No. 10: Report on digital health access

12.1. Characterization

We evaluate the impact and effectiveness of MyHealth, the digital health platform introduced by the Catalan regional government in 2008. We address the following specific research questions: how have patients utilised the MyHealth app over time, and what patterns have emerged in its usage; the exacerbation or mitigation of the generational digital divide in healthcare access and utilisation; the impact on the primary care system in Catalonia, particularly in terms of cost-effectiveness. The final aim is to identify trends, challenges, and opportunities associated with implementing MyHealth and provide insights to inform future developments in digital health initiatives in Catalonia and beyond.

Table 13. General information of Exploitable Result No. 10

Name of the Exploitable Results	Report on digital health access
Type of results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge

	<input type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Status of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Brief description of the result	Identifying the evolution of access to MyHealth App and implications on healthcare use
Partner/s responsible for the results	UIC
Work Package related to the results	WP8

12.1.1. Alternative solutions

N/A

12.1.2. Target Market

N/A

12.1.3. Stakeholder

- Policymakers

12.2. Exploitation Roadmap

To maximise the impact of knowledge on the factors influencing the use digital health access, we will make the policy report, and we will share it with stakeholders (Public Health Department, Regional Health Ministry). Additionally, the findings will be disseminated through high-impact publications (scientific articles), presentations during conferences.

13. Exploitable Result No. 11: Research/policy report describing the best practices for the provision of digital health services by doctors

13.1. Characterization

The objective is to identify factors influencing the use of phone consultations in primary care. This research investigates how GP medical practices need to adapt for teleconsultation delivery and examines the role of contextual factors, in shaping doctors’ provision of services and patients’ demand. Drawing on findings from a scoping review, focus groups with doctors, and a patient survey, we aim to formulate evidence-based recommendations for a broad range of decision-makers, from government and payer representatives to healthcare providers. Our innovative approach, employing vignette methodology and mixed-methods research, may inspire other researchers, particularly those interested in evidence-based health policymaking and research with highly relevant applications to current teleconsultation policy.

The report will also address the equity dimension related to the diffusion of digital technologies, based on the results of the research activities carried out as part of Task 8.3. The aim is to analyze the uptake of digital health services among both doctors and patients while trying to understand whether these services may also

be a source of inequality by, for instance, creating disparities based on the resources or skills their use requires.

Table 14. General information of Exploitable Result No. 11

Name of the Exploitable Results	Research/policy report describing the best practices for the provision of digital health services by doctors
Type of results	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> New Knowledge <input type="checkbox"/> Methods and tools <input type="checkbox"/> Activities <input type="checkbox"/> New partnerships & stakeholders engagement
Status of the result	Identification of who has digital health access for healthcare utilisation
Brief description of the result	<input type="checkbox"/> Potential <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Under development <input type="checkbox"/> Achieved
Partner/s responsible for the results	SGH
Work Package related to the results	WP8

13.1.1. Alternative solutions

Not applicable

13.1.2. Target Market

Not applicable

13.1.3. Stakeholder

- Policy makers
- Regulatory agencies
- Scientific community
- Healthcare industries

13.2. Exploitation Roadmap

To maximize the impact of sharing knowledge on the factors influencing the use of phone consultations and other digital technologies, we will prepare the policy report and we will share it with stakeholders (e.g., Ministry of Health, medical associations, the National Health Fund in Poland, providers of digital services). Additionally, the findings will be disseminated through high-impact publications (scientific articles), presentations during conferences, and via digital platforms, including social media like LinkedIn website for the FLASH project and websites.

14. Exploitation activities carried out in the first two years of FLASH

During the first two years of the project, some activity related to the exploitation of FLASH results has already been carried out. Project partners participated in a series of dissemination events in order to present the results mainly to the scientific community but also to key stakeholders of the project such as policymakers. In [Table] is presented an overview of the presentations mentioned.

FLASH – Flexible Approaches to Support Health through financing

Partner	WP	Date	Activity	Description	Stakeholders
MCI	WP5	21/10/2023	Speech Markus Frischhut on: The EU 'patient mobility'-acquis in the light of the new concept of a 'European Health Union	International Conference "European Health Union: Perspectives and challenges", organized by the Aristotle University Thessaloniki (AuTH) Laboratory for the Study of Medical Law and Bioethics in cooperation with the National Commission for Bioethics and Technoethics, the Thessaloniki Bar Association and the Thessaloniki Medical Association	Scientific and research community
UNIVR	WP6	9-10/11/2023	Speech Emanuel Bracco, part of the team of UNIVR (Prof Pertile and Bertoli) concerning research activity of WP6. Title of the presentation: HEALTH NEEDS AND RESOURCES: ALLOCATION AND MEASUREMENT ISSUES	Conference organized by the University of Urbino dedicated to discuss health needs, resource allocation, and planning	Scientific and research community
KZP	WP5	20/12/2023	Seminar on Reimbursement Decree	The conference was held in National institute of Economy (NHÚ – Národohospodářský ústav), in Prague. The main topics of the discussion were the role of Reimbursement Decree in healthcare systems, the shape of the Reimbursement Decree for 2024 and its impact.	Scientific and research community
CU	WP5	4-5/09/2023	Field trips in Work Package 5	Workshop on 04./05. September in Gmünd, Lower Austria, on the genesis, development and experience of their projects. Workshop on 10-11 September in Furth im Wald, Germany, on current challenges in emergency care services across borders. Colleagues from the Univerzita Karlova and the MCI The Entrepreneurial School® were able to participate in the second field trip.	Scientific and research community
UNIVR	WP6	26/01/2024	Vulnerabilità – Un approccio interdisciplinare	On 25th of January, Paolo Pertile has spoken at the event "Vulnerabilità – Un approccio interdisciplinare", organized by the Lanza Foundation. The speech focused on the vulnerability of healthcare systems, which is part of the research agenda of the project FLASH. In particular, the focus has been on vulnerabilities related to the mechanism of healthcare financing and their efficiency and equity implications.	Scientific and research community
MCI	WP5	19/09/2024	Speech Markus Frischhut on Patient mobility between individual and collective rights: transformation based on solidarity at the 9th Conference of the European Association of Health Law	Cross-border healthcare has mainly been shaped by individual patients enforcing their rights under Regulation social security coordination and especially also the (passive) freedom of services under EU primary law. This has led to an acquis of rights, as today codified in EU Directive patient mobility. The focal point of the pandemic has shown that this system driven by individuals sometimes lacks a collective notion of solidarity. Solidarity is one of the EU's general (Art. 2 TEU) and one of the EU's health values (2006 Council conclusions), as well as a key element of the concept of the EU Health Union. Hence, the question arises, if the status quo of the EU cross-border healthcare acquis sufficiently embeds this value. Based on the findings of a 'Horizon Europe' funded research project, this contribution argues that it is time to merge the EU regulation and the EU directive in this field, in order to simplify the legal situation for patients. Such an endeavor would also offer the opportunity, to put a stronger emphasis on solidarity. One way to achieve this would be joint planning, not only for rare diseases but also in other fields. Better coordination should also take place with regard to excess capacities, i.e. planning hospital bed excess capacity at EU level. In addition, solidarity across borders shall also take place in enhanced cooperation	Scientific and research community; policymakers

				in border regions. Finally, several ideas that did not make it into Directive patient mobility are worth reconsidering for more solidarity in cross-border healthcare.	
UNIVR	WP4	18-20/11/2024	Poster presentation at ISPOR Europe 2024 (Barcelona)	The work proposes a flexible model for the systematic use of Markov models in Budget IMPACT Analysis (BIA). Although it is crucial for both payers and manufacturers to forecast the impact of innovation over time, the methods usually adopted fail to account for all the real-world complexities. Although Markov modeling is suggested as a desirable approach in several guidelines, it is very rarely applied. The proposed model is flexible, as it can be used to evaluate different technologies, by providing the necessary inputs. I also show that a data parsimonious implementation is possible, by introducing some additional assumptions, significantly improving the accessibility of more accurate dynamic BI forecasts for both payers and manufacturers.	Scientific community, policy makers, biomedical industry

In addition to these presentations FLASH has organized two international workshops targeting the scientific community. The details of these events are reported below:

i. **VII Workshop of Immigration, Health and Wellbeing**

On 13-14th of June 2024, at the "Accademia di Agricoltura Scienze e Lettere" the VII Workshop of Immigration, Health and Wellbeing was held. During the event it has been possible to exchange insight regarding preventive care for immigrants, labour market impacts, health policy, and much more. Also, it was an occasion to present the activities, and the results achieved in the context of the project.

ii. **Workshop on Primary Health Care: Exploring Databases**

On November 11, 2024, the University of Verona hosted the workshop Primary Health Care: Exploring Databases, bringing together experts to delve into advancements in primary care data. The event featured presentations and insights into international and regional databases, and a collaborative round table on improving general medicine strategies in Italy. The discussions underscored the transformative role of data in enhancing health outcomes. Also, it was an occasion to present the activities, and the results achieved in the context of the project

Finally, in the first two years of the project three journal articles were published in the context of the project, two of which are related to the results described in this document. The details are reported in [TABLE]:

Ttitle	Author s	Month/Yea r	DOI	Journa l	Relativ e Result
With a little help from my (neighbouring) friends. 'Border region patient mobility' in the European	Markus Frischhut; Rosella Levaggi	June 2024	10.1016/j.healthpol.2024.105114	Health Policy	#7

Union: A policy analysis					
Information provision and financial incentives in Catalonia's public primary care (2010–2019): an interrupted time series analysis	Roger Esteban-Fabró, Ermengol Coma, Eduardo Hermosilla, Leonardo Méndez-Boo, Carolina Guiriguet, Gabriel Facchini, Catia Nicodemo, Josep Vidal-Alaball	October 2024	10.1016/j.lanepe.2024.101102	The Lancet Regional Health - Europe	#8